

COVER SHEET FOR PROPOSAL TO THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

PROGRAM ANNOUNCEMENT/SOLICITATION NO./CLOSING DATE/if not in response to a program announcement/solicitation enter NSF 04-23					FOR NSF USE ONLY	
FOR CONSIDERATION BY NSF ORGANIZATION UNIT(S) (Indicate the most specific unit known, i.e. program, division, etc.)					NSF PROPOSAL NUMBER	
ARC - ARCTIC RESRCH SUPPRT & LOGISTI					0613127	
DATE RECEIVED	NUMBER OF COPIES	DIVISION ASSIGNED	FUND CODE	DUNS# (Data Universal Numbering System)	FILE LOCATION	
12/31/2005	2	14010000 ARC	5205	796268548	12/31/2005 9:53pm	
EMPLOYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (EIN) OR TAXPAYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (TIN)		SHOW PREVIOUS AWARD NO. IF THIS IS <input type="checkbox"/> A RENEWAL <input type="checkbox"/> AN ACCOMPLISHMENT-BASED RENEWAL		IS THIS PROPOSAL BEING SUBMITTED TO ANOTHER FEDERAL AGENCY? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> IF YES, LIST ACRONYM(S)		
		0101279				
NAME OF ORGANIZATION TO WHICH AWARD SHOULD BE MADE			ADDRESS OF AWARDEE ORGANIZATION, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			
AWARDEE ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)			3535 College Road, Suite 101			
5300001191			Fairbanks, AK. 997093710			
NAME OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT FROM ABOVE			ADDRESS OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
PERFORMING ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)						
IS AWARDEE ORGANIZATION (Check All That Apply) (See GPG II.C For Definitions)		<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> FOR-PROFIT ORGANIZATION		<input type="checkbox"/> MINORITY BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> WOMAN-OWNED BUSINESS		<input type="checkbox"/> IF THIS IS A PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL THEN CHECK HERE
TITLE OF PROPOSED PROJECT Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program						
REQUESTED AMOUNT	PROPOSED DURATION (1-60 MONTHS)	REQUESTED STARTING DATE	SHOW RELATED PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL NO. IF APPLICABLE			
\$ 1,188,044	5 months					
CHECK APPROPRIATE BOX(ES) IF THIS PROPOSAL INCLUDES ANY OF THE ITEMS LISTED BELOW						
<input type="checkbox"/> BEGINNING INVESTIGATOR (GPG I.A)			<input type="checkbox"/> HUMAN SUBJECTS (GPG II.D.6)			
<input type="checkbox"/> DISCLOSURE OF LOBBYING ACTIVITIES (GPG II.C)			Exemption Subsection _____ or IRB App. Date _____			
<input type="checkbox"/> PROPRIETARY & PRIVILEGED INFORMATION (GPG I.B, II.C.1.d)			<input type="checkbox"/> INTERNATIONAL COOPERATIVE ACTIVITIES: COUNTRY/COUNTRIES INVOLVED (GPG II.C.2.j)			
<input type="checkbox"/> HISTORIC PLACES (GPG II.C.2.j)						
<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL GRANT FOR EXPLOR. RESEARCH (SGER) (GPG II.D.1)						
<input type="checkbox"/> VERTEBRATE ANIMALS (GPG II.D.5) IACUC App. Date _____			<input type="checkbox"/> HIGH RESOLUTION GRAPHICS/OTHER GRAPHICS WHERE EXACT COLOR REPRESENTATION IS REQUIRED FOR PROPER INTERPRETATION (GPG I.G.1)			
PI/PD DEPARTMENT		PI/PD POSTAL ADDRESS				
ARCUS		3535 College Road, Suite 101				
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CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the individual applicant or the authorized official of the applicant institution is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), as set forth in Grant Proposal Guide (GPG), NSF 04-23. Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, the authorized official of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of Grant Policy Manual Section 510; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

Drug Free Work Place Certification

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Drug Free Work Place Certification contained in Appendix C of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Debarment and Suspension Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Appendix D of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

This certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

(1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.

(2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.

(3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, Title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE		SIGNATURE	DATE
NAME Wendy K Warnick		Electronic Signature	Dec 31 2005 9:37PM
TELEPHONE NUMBER 907-474-1600	ELECTRONIC MAIL ADDRESS warnick@arcus.org	FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604	

*SUBMISSION OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBERS IS VOLUNTARY AND WILL NOT AFFECT THE ORGANIZATION'S ELIGIBILITY FOR AN AWARD. HOWEVER, THEY ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM AND ASSIST IN PROCESSING THE PROPOSAL. SSN SOLICITED UNDER NSF ACT OF 1950, AS AMENDED.

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279). The supplement of \$1,188,044 to the funds already awarded is necessary because of several new activities that ARCUS will undertake on behalf of the arctic research community and the National Science Foundation (NSF). This supplement request also extends the expiration date of the award to 31 August 2006 to accommodate key events and transitional activities that must continue beyond the end of the current expiration date of this cooperative agreement, 31 March 2006.

The activities described in this request for supplemental funds fall under the following major tasks identified in the cooperative agreement: 1) Arctic Community Science Planning; 2) NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination; 3) Arctic Science Education; 4) Information and Outreach; and 5) Core Support. Several of the added activities described here provide community science management for NSF-funded research programs, coordinate research-focused community workshops and meetings, expand education and outreach opportunities for undergraduate and graduate students and for teachers and researchers, and provide important information to scientists, educators, and policy makers. All of the activities support community science planning or provide information and support for the conduct of arctic research.

Accomplishments between April 2005 and the present are outlined only for those activities for which supplemental funding is requested. This information is included to provide context of the work that ARCUS is doing through this cooperative agreement and the basis on which supplemental funding is requested. The projected activities between January and August 2006 and those activities for which supplemental funding is requested also are summarized. All activities described fall under existing tasks and the current scope of the cooperative agreement.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.4 Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Planning and Coordination

The SEARCH science management function transitioned from the University of Washington to ARCUS in Spring 2005. ARCUS worked with the NSF Program Director, SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) Chair and committee members, and the former Science Management Office (SMO) at the University of Washington to facilitate the transition and to plan and implement a variety of activities. In that time, ARCUS developed and launched a new SEARCH website, appointed panel members for the three SEARCH implementation panels—Observing, Understanding, and Responding to Change, convened the SEARCH Implementation Workshop held in May 2005, edited and published the workshop report, convened a SEARCH Science Steering Committee meeting in December 2005, and conducted a number of other scientific program development and planning activities on behalf of the SEARCH program.

The requested supplemental funding will support several new SEARCH planning and coordination activities, including support for the Chair of the International ASOF Program through a subcontract with the Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture Science (CEFAS), the implementation and facilitation of SEARCH working groups, and a SEARCH Science Steering Committee meeting in June 2006.

Accomplishments

- Worked with planning committee, the SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC), and federal agency representatives to plan and convene the SEARCH Implementation Workshop,

held in May 2005 in Lansdowne, VA, to establish priorities for the next steps of the implementation of SEARCH. Over 90 participants attended, including members of the SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC); the Observing Change, Understanding Change, and Responding to Change Panels; the SEARCH Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC); as well as other invited participants.

- Completed and published the final report from the Implementation Workshop: *Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond* in close cooperation with SEARCH workshop participants and research community. The report details specific science priorities for SEARCH activity areas and underwent several iterations of community review. The full report is available online as a downloadable PDF and 500 copies were printed for distribution.
- Organized the SEARCH SSC Meeting in Fairbanks, AK in December 2005. Worked with SSC Chair, Panel Chairs, and IPMC Chair to develop the agenda, meeting materials, and to facilitate meeting discussions.
- Assisted the SSC Chair with preparation of presentations and proposals to increase connections to international programs, including the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC), Developing Arctic Modelling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES), and the International Polar Year (IPY). Other outreach activities included the submission of a proposal for a special session at the November 2006 Earth System Science Partnership Open Science Conference on Global Environmental Change.
- Organized several SEARCH teleconferences, including those for the SSC Executive Committee, Panels, and Implementation Workshop Organizing Committee.

Planned Activities; Currently Funded

- Work with the SEARCH SSC Chair and IPMC to implement membership rotation for the SSC and support appropriate SSC science planning activities.
- Continue to facilitate Panel activities, including increasing coordination with agency representatives and follow-up activities to the SEARCH Implementation Workshop.
- Continue development and finalize searchable online SEARCH Research Activity Database to track and communicate SEARCH-funded and SEARCH-related research projects, initiatives, and programs, in consultation with an *ad hoc* committee.
- Ongoing SEARCH website development and updates.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- Continue assistance with international coordination activities as needed, including support of the Chair of the International ASOF Program and assistance with coordinating SEARCH IPY activities.
- Coordinate the creation and appointment, and facilitate activities of, three standing SEARCH Working Groups on Data Management, Paleoenvironment, and Education and Outreach.
- Work with SSC and IPMC Chairs to organize and convene a SSC Meeting in June 2006.
- Commence planning for 2007 State of the Arctic Conference; convene initial planning committee and begin discussions on timing, focus, and content of conference.

1.5 Bering Ecosystem Research Program Planning and Coordination

For the past several years the NSF Arctic Sciences Section has supported the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST), a planning process to initiate collaborative studies of the sub-arctic seas, culminating in cooperative ecological research of the eastern, western, and basin areas by Japan, Russia and the United States. ARCUS provides organizational support and coordination of activities for the BEST science planning process. BEST priorities for research, published in the BEST science plan in October 2004, were included in the Fall 2005 NSF Arctic Sciences Section announcement of opportunity.

Accomplishments

- Distribution of the BEST science plan is ongoing. 1000 copies were printed; 350 copies have been sent in response to requests and several hundred more have been distributed at meetings.
- Coordinated BEST Science Steering Committee (SSC) teleconferences March through June 2005 to discuss tasks for development of BEST implementation plan.
- Prepared and submitted article on BEST and ESSAS for the Consortium for Oceanographic Research and Education (CORE) newsletter; article published 2 May 2005.
- Coordinated travel arrangements and support for U.S. invited speakers, SSC members, and students (total of 20 people) to BEST Implementation Workshop (16 May) and GLOBEC Sub-Arctic Seas Symposium (16-20 May), working closely with PICES and GLOBEC staff.
- Attended BEST Implementation Workshop and GLOBEC symposium, provided materials (science plan and draft implementation plans), developed participant list, and gathered and distributed presentation materials and comments received on the draft plan.
- Coordinated plans, travel arrangements and support for SSC meeting 13-14 June in Seattle (total of 8 people). Attended SSC meeting, provided materials, and facilitated SSC planning for revisions to draft implementation plan.
- Worked closely with University of Washington BEST project office in developing and finalizing the BEST implementation plan. Prepared and posted the review draft and solicited comments from the research community; worked closely with UW BEST project office and SSC in revising drafts, and posted final version of plan on the BEST website in September 2005.
- Distribution of the implementation plan is ongoing. Hard copies are printed as needed; approximately 100 hard copies have been distributed. The implementation plan is also available on the website as a downloadable PDF.
- Assisted in preparing report on BEST activities to the SEARCH SSC.

Planned Activities; Currently Funded

- Assist in planning for proposed PICES-ESSAS workshop to be held in St. Petersburg, June 2006. Coordinate travel arrangements and support for George Hunt to attend.
- Ongoing document distribution and website maintenance and updating.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- Following the announcement of BEST awards (anticipated in April 2006), plan and coordinate SSC teleconferences and a face-to-face meeting, as needed, to coordinate the development of an integrated research program and to guide fieldwork.

1.8 Arctic Research Data Coordination and Data Management Needs Assessment

A clear need has emerged through a number of arctic planning activities, conferences and meetings for improved data coordination and management across disciplines, research programs, and agencies. There is a particularly strong need for coordination of geospatial data, as acquisition and development of such data has proliferated with tremendous potential for advancing science through a variety of cyberinfrastructure applications, including Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) and related technologies.

We have requested to reprogram funds remaining from the ALIAS project, on which development has been discontinued, to plan and convene a two-day capacity-building workshop for selected community leaders as a forum for input into the implementation of integrated arctic spatial data management. The workshop will assemble 15-20 representatives to discuss community recommendations and to provide training for a core group of community leaders. In addition to providing information for an arctic research data coordination and data management needs assessment (the activity supported through current funding), this workshop will build on and contribute to an effort entitled "Community Needs Assessment and Portal Prototype Development for an Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure," a proposal submitted to the NSF's Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section as a Small Grant for Exploratory Research (SGER). Supplemental funds are not requested for this activity.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

ARCUS provides organizational support and science planning coordination and facilitates research community planning activities for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section. The additional activities planned under this major task include support for the ARCSS Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program.

2.2 ARCSS Program Coordination

ARCUS continues to provide community science management and coordination of activities for the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program. The ARCSS Program has continued to focus on synthesis activities aimed at achieving system-level understanding of the Arctic. Program coordination activities reported below have been designed to facilitate the synthesis effort and have included increased community input and development of a new ARCSS Program science planning process. The additional planned activities will continue to facilitate a focus on system-level research and foster strong interdisciplinary collaboration.

Accomplishments

- Worked with the ARCSS Committee to organize and convene two online "eTown Meetings" in April 2005, held to solicit community input on the ARCSS science planning process and attended by over 50 total participants.

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- Worked with the ARCSS Committee to organize and convene an online "Synthesis eTown Meeting" in October 2005, held to solicit community input on ARCSS Synthesis priorities and attended by over 60 participants.
 - Organized the ARCSS Committee face-to-face meeting in October 2005; worked with the ARCSS Committee Executive Committee and NSF Program Director to develop the agenda, meeting materials, and facilitate meeting discussions.
 - Supported nine ARCSS meetings of opportunity at the American Geophysical Union Conference in San Francisco through logistics, organizational, and website assistance.
 - Supported emerging Communities of Practice—groups of researchers organized around a set of arctic system science questions—with planning and community development, including teleconference/webconference support and creation of online collaboration tools.
 - Provided support for the group of funded Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) projects/investigators, including support of individual project teleconferences, creation of investigator email list, and organization of several online meetings.
 - Provided support for group of funded Study of the Northern Alaska Coastal System (SNACS) projects, including creation of email list, update and hosting of website and meeting planning assistance.
 - Provided support and guidance, through a subcontract with the University of Alaska Fairbanks, for a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) project office to promote community development and coordinate human dimension research activities relevant to arctic system research.
 - Organized and convened several ARCSS Committee teleconferences on topics such as science planning, synthesis, and data management.
 - Worked with the ARCSS Committee and the NSF ARCSS Program Director to facilitate and coordinate the development of another ARCSS Announcement of Opportunity (AO) aimed at synthesizing knowledge of the arctic system. The AO is intended as an additional step in the ongoing ARCSS Program plan for a large-scale arctic synthesis effort.
 - Supported and assisted the ARCSS Committee chair in planning, guiding, advising and leading the ARCSS Program community science planning and synthesis process.

Planned Activities; Currently Funded

- Ongoing organization and support of community eTown Meetings; topics of planned eTown Meetings include data management and update of ARCSS science priorities.
- Launch series of science-focused "Webseminars," community-organized online seminars on scientific topics relevant to arctic system research; planned topics in near-term include the role of scale in arctic science and freshwater synthesis.
- In collaboration with the ARCSS Committee and NSF Program Director, organize and convene March 2006 ARCSS Committee Meeting in Seattle, WA.
- Develop and launch a new ARCSS website that reflects current science focus, priorities, and activities.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- Implement a subcontract with the Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory (CRREL) to support a SNACS synthesis coordinator.

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- Provide support to additional existing ARCSS research activities, including hosting of Paleoenvironmental Arctic Sciences (PARCS) synthesis website and teleconference/webconference support for Western Arctic Shelf-Basin Interactions (SBI) planning.
 - Continue organizational support of Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) funded projects, including convening a March 2006 meeting in Seattle, WA, providing travel and logistics support for that meeting, developing a SASS project website, and support for a SASS synthesis coordinator located with a selected SASS project.

2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Program Community Science Planning

The NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program is a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary program that encompasses all social sciences research supported by NSF. The Arctic Social Sciences Program supports research that documents and analyzes the dynamic cultures, economies, and technologies of northern populations.

ARCUS provides support to the Arctic Social Sciences Program by bringing together social scientists of diverse disciplines as well as researchers from other fields to promote cross-disciplinary collaboration and by working with the research community and arctic residents to develop science priorities and plans. Additionally, ARCUS supports several information and outreach activities on behalf of the Arctic Social Sciences Program.

No planning or science coordination activities have been undertaken since April 2005 with the exception of preliminary discussions and planning with the NSF Arctic Social Sciences program manager and representatives of several organizations for a project to update the International Directory of Arctic Social Scientists and make it accessible in a searchable, easily updated online database.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- ARCUS will support the research and development necessary to update the International Directory of Arctic Social Scientists, through a consulting contract with Robert Wheelersburg, and in collaboration with the International Arctic Social Sciences Association and other international partners.
- The Directory will be made publicly available through a searchable, easily updated online database.

2.3.4 Bering Sea Community Planning

ARCUS provides support for the development of a plan for Bering Sea social science research and the plan's integration and implementation with the current Bering Sea Ecosystem Study (BEST) science plan.

Accomplishments

- Worked closely with the *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Plan* drafting committee to develop related website materials and online comment forms; posted planning documents and solicited review and comment.
- Posted the draft science plan and solicited review and comment; mailed hard copies of materials to Bering Sea adjacent community representatives.

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- Assisted in planning for a special session focused on community and stakeholder involvement on 8 February 2006 as part of the Alaska Forum on the Environment conference in Anchorage, Alaska.

Planned Activities; Currently Funded

- Coordinate plans, travel arrangements, and support for presenters and selected participants for the community-focused session 8 February 2006 at Alaska Forum on the Environment conference in Anchorage, Alaska.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- Following announcement of BEST awards (anticipated in April 2006), plan and coordinate teleconferences and/or face-to-face meeting, as needed, to coordinate the development of an integrated research program and to guide fieldwork.
- Prepare, produce, and distribute the final version of *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Plan* and distribute as appropriate. Maintain and update website content.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS implemented an Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in January 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community, to nurture understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents, and to improve public understanding of arctic research.

The program accomplishments since April 2005 and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. The supplemental funds requested would support Arctic Visiting Speakers tours from April through August 2006.

Accomplishments

- Seven AVS tours have taken place since March 2005, addressing arctic issues at 15 different public engagements. Speakers presented at a variety of venues including visitor centers, a library, schools, workshops, and on the radio.
- Over 650 people attended the public presentations.
- Of the seven speaking tours, six U.S. speakers visited institutions within the U.S. and one U.S. speaker traveled to Greenland and Denmark to lecture.
- Topics included northern hydrology, potential impacts of climate change in the Arctic, tundra plants and climate change, insects overwintering in extreme cold, urbanization of American Indian and Inuit communities, and Iñupiat whaling and environmental changes.
- Seven new speakers were added to the Speaker's Bureau, which currently has 52 profiles for potential Arctic Visiting Speakers. The contact and biographical information for existing members of the Speaker's Bureau was also verified and updated.
- Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series brochures were distributed at various conferences.

Planned Activities

- Continue to promote the use of the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to facilitate collaboration

and information sharing about arctic research and the Arctic, including distribution of program information via ArcticInfo.

- Advertise the AVS series more extensively among arctic residents; encourage participation by indigenous experts as visiting speakers and by arctic communities as host institutions.
- Post AVS information to several educational e-mail listserves around the country to stimulate interest from the K-12 education community to apply as host institutions.
- Support up to five additional speaker tours through August 2006. Applications from three host institutions have already been received for this period.
- Continue to recruit individuals for the Speakers Bureau.
- Continue to provide updated information about speaker tours on the ARCUS website.
- Revise and update the online application and evaluation forms.
- Post presentation videos and other materials sent to ARCUS by host institutions and speakers on the Internet Media Archive.

3.5 Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC)

The Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program is an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in arctic research, working closely with scientists as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry. Participating TREC teachers serve as a foundation for a growing community of students, educators, researchers and the general public that is engaged in science teaching and learning. Through TREC, teachers will have the opportunity to increase their knowledge, enhance teaching skills, transfer their experiences to the classroom, engage in leadership roles, and develop a supportive network of researchers and education colleagues.

The accomplishments since April 2005 and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. Supplemental funding will support the program activities from April through August 2006, including the completion of the selection and matching process for TREC 2006 teachers and researchers, development and implementation of a series of teacher and researcher orientation webinars, planning and implementation of the face-to-face orientation and safety training for teachers, coordinating the development of an education and logistics plan for each teacher-researcher team, and support of the teacher's educational and outreach activities before, during and after the field phase of their TREC 2006 expedition. Additional activities will be continued into the next cooperative agreement year.

Accomplishments

- Held four Connecting Arctic/Antarctic Researchers and Educators (CARE) meetings between March and June 2005 using the HorizonWimba online meeting interface. CARE is a professional development network developed as part of TREC, through which teachers and scientists can further their work to bring polar research into classrooms. CARE meetings were attended by both TEA (Teachers Experiencing Antarctica and the Arctic) and TREC teachers and included a presentation by either an Arctic or Antarctic researcher.
- Facilitated several TREC outreach activities, including attendance by two TREC teachers at the National Science Teachers Association (NSTA) conference in Dallas, TX; a TREC presentation by TREC teacher Amy Clapp and researcher Max Holmes at the Conference on

Teacher Researcher Experiences held at the University of Rhode Island; ARCUS staff participation at the "Poles Together" education workshop in Boulder, CO; and a presentation by ARCUS staff and TREC teacher Steve Marshall at the Fall 2005 AGU Conference session on "Teacher Professional Development Programs Promoting Authentic Scientific Research in the Classroom".

- Developed and updated TREC brochures and a TREC poster and distributed them at relevant conferences and meetings.
- Developed and produced a four-minute outreach video on the TREC program, using digital photographs and video footage taken by TREC teachers during their field experiences. The TREC informational video was presented at the Fall 2005 AGU Conference and is available on the TREC website.
- Organized, convened, and facilitated several orientation activities for the TREC 2005 expeditions, including TREC orientation "webinars," TREC logistics planning conference calls to discuss field preparations and logistics, and an in-person Orientation and Safety Training in Fairbanks, AK.
- Coordinated and facilitated the seven TREC field research experiences in the Arctic from June through October 2005, including development, maintenance, and update of website content, bulletin boards, and photo galleries.
- Coordinated and supported 11 *Arctic Alive!* events using the Horizon Wimba platform to connect the TREC teachers and researchers working in the Arctic to classrooms, libraries, science centers, and other venues all over the world.
- Provided website and TREC Virtual Base Camp support and development for two additional teacher research experience projects (i.e., research vessel expedition in the Bering Sea and an Antarctica expedition).
- Held seven individual follow-up calls between ARCUS, 2005 TREC teachers and their researcher or research team to discuss the research experience, plans for future collaborations, and approaches to taking the research and the research experience into the classroom.
- Organized and convened a TREC Informational Webinar in November 2005 for teachers and researchers interested in learning more about TREC prior to applying to the TREC 2006 program.
- Implemented the 2006 TREC application process and accepted 2006 TREC teacher and researcher applications from November through December 2005.
- Began selection process for TREC 2006 projects; a selection committee for the TREC 2006 teachers and researchers was appointed and preparations for 2006 TREC review and selection process began, including the compilation of applications and refinement of the selection criteria and process.

Planned Activities

- Coordinate and host a "live from Antarctica" event in January 2006 with teacher Dena Rosenberger and members of her research team, using the online HorizonWimba platform.
- Coordinate selection and matching of TREC teachers with research projects in January and February 2006.

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- Plan and schedule TREC orientation activities, including a webinar series and a face-to-face training on using TREC communication technologies and safety in the field.
 - Provide a compiled list of TREC 2005 public outreach activities to NSF.
 - Convene teleconferences with teacher/researcher teams, ARCUS staff, and VECO Polar resources to plan 2006 field logistics.
 - Prepare abstracts and TREC outreach materials for relevant conferences and workshops.
 - Hold three CARE meetings, including TREC and TEA teachers and Arctic and Antarctic researchers.
 - Support TREC teacher/researcher teams in planning and implementing education and outreach activities before, during, and after the field expedition.
 - Support the TREC teacher/researcher teams during the field expedition phase between April and September 2006, providing technical and content support for Virtual Base Camp journaling, Ask the Teacher and Researcher Q&A, and posting to the photo gallery.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter

Witness the Arctic is a biannual newsletter, available online and in hardcopy, which provides information on current arctic research and education efforts and news, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic science, research support and logistics, profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts, and calendar events and publications. With edited contributions from representatives throughout the arctic research and education community, *Witness the Arctic* is a substantive and significant source of information.

The accomplishments since April 2005 and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. Supplemental funding will support the newsletter planning, development, and publication from April through August 2006.

Accomplishments

- Completed the Winter 2004/2005 (Volume 11, number 2) issue of the newsletter. Distributed to 5,800 U.S. and 3,500 international subscribers. The newsletter featured an article on Arctic Climate Impact Assessment, as well as the standard sections on NSF programs and activities, science news, and international news.
- In addition to the initial distribution to subscribers, the electronic version was posted on the ARCUS website for download; hard copies are available and distributed in response to requests.
- Planned contents, solicited contributions, edited submissions, and drafted material for Volume 12, number 1. The feature article for this issue is on NSF's broader impacts criteria, relevance to arctic research, and examples of successful programs.

Planned activities

- The expected publication date for Volume 12, number 1 is late January 2006. Estimated distribution will be to 6,150 U.S. and 3,900 international subscribers; the electronic version will be available for download.

-
- Begin work on Volume 12, number 2. Determine feature story topic, solicit contributions for all sections, edit submissions, and draft material for this issue. Expected publication date is September 2006.

4.2 Website/Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and serves over 6,000 files from over 2,000 pages. The website is the focal point for web-served educational programs such as TREC, various community science planning tools, and provides important information and resources to the research community about key research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications. The ARCUS website represents a valuable source of information for the general public about arctic research, a forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers, approaches for integrating arctic research with educational programs, and access to other researchers, programs, and stakeholders working in the Arctic.

The accomplishments since April 2005 and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing website development, management and maintenance from April through August 2006.

Accomplishments

- Created, maintained, and updated sections of the website for ARCUS-facilitated programs, meetings, and workshops described in other activity descriptions in this report.
- Posted on-line versions of various arctic research publications for community access and downloading.
- Improved file structure and site architecture for major sections of the website.
- Developed improved navigation menus (utilizing PHP) for the SEARCH and TREC sections of the website.
- Developed additional stylesheets for improved consistency in visual layout.
- Implemented new technology and software for bulletin board applications (e.g., TREC Virtual Base Camp) for improved security and user functionality.
- Improved database-driven solutions (using SQL and PHP) with improved searchability and data sorting functionality for use in applications such as the Internet Media Archive, searchable project databases and a publication database.
- Designed and implemented a "Community Workspace," a content management system that allows collaboration between members of the arctic research and education communities through participation in workgroups; workgroup members can share documents and images, edit shared content, post news and events, and participate in threaded forum discussions.
- Continued to improve accessibility standards and code-compliance throughout the website.

Planned Activities

- Ongoing improvement to file structure and site architecture for efficient management of website.
- Ongoing development of database and community workspace tools as needed for a variety of programs and activities.

-
- Development of design and code standards to increase consistency throughout sections of the website.
 - Ongoing development and update of content as needed.

4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver

ARCUS developed and manages the ArcticInfo Listserver, a "broadcast only" list with high quality, accuracy-checked, and well-edited content that provides information and important announcements to the international arctic research community. There have been 2,252 announcements distributed from ArcticInfo since its creation in September 1996. Each year has seen an increase in submissions for distribution and in subscribers. Currently about half of the subscribers are from the United States and half from other countries.

The accomplishments since April 2005 and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance from April through August 2006.

Accomplishments

- Received, reviewed, accepted or declined, edited, and formatted over 350 submissions to ArcticInfo.
- Distributed 293 announcements from April 2005 to present, including notices on funding opportunities, important events, publications, and position announcements. On average, approximately 35 announcements were posted per month.
- Communicated with subscribers regarding announcements, special information requests, subscribe or unsubscribe requests, and other concerns.
- Maintained a searchable online archive of all posted announcements.
- The listserv had 492 new subscribers in this period, resulting in 5,120 current subscribers.
- Maintained a database to track subscription activity.
- Managed the "bounce list" by researching bounced announcements to correct and update addresses, investigate apparently dead domains, and delete addresses that consistently bounced back from the subscriber list.
- In addition to managing ArcticInfo, ARCUS has created and manages 16 additional electronic lists for the arctic research community. These lists range from small group lists for community planning groups or science steering committees to large "community of researcher" lists, similar to but less comprehensive than ArcticInfo. Some of the lists are "participatory," meaning that any subscribed participant can post to the lists, and some are "broadcast only," meaning that only designated people can post content to the lists.

Planned Activities

- Continue to review, edit, and format ArcticInfo submissions. Post new announcements to the list and add them to the online archive.
- Continue to communicate with subscribers and organizations and individuals who wish to use the list for information distribution or access.
- Continue to track subscription activity and research "bounced" addresses.

-
- Continue advertising, maintenance, and management of the list.
 - Continue to manage the additional arctic research community lists and develop additional lists, as needed and requested.

4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers

The Directory of Arctic Researchers was initiated in 1994 to aid links among individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders and to facilitate arctic research and education efforts. The contents of the directory have been developed through extensive surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions.

The accomplishments since April 2005, and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance of the Directory from April through August 2006.

Accomplishments

- Added 348 new records since April 2005. Presently there are a total of 4,309 individual records in the Directory.
- Surveyed researchers with current Directory records to obtain updated contact and current research information.
- Surveyed significant international research organizations and individuals to expand non-U.S. researcher records in the database.
- Maintained and regularly updated a downloadable PDF of the Directory, including alphabetically listed individual researcher entries and a cross-reference file listing researchers within science specialty categories. Developed a new Directory PDF design and creation process, which streamlined the PDF creation and results in a smaller file size.

Planned Activities

- Implement an automated daily update of the online Directory, which will include an automated daily Directory PDF creation and uploading process.
- Develop web services to allow interactions (pulling and pushing information) with other arctic databases such as the CEON-IMS, Barrow Area Information Database-Internet Map Server, and the VECO Polar Resources ARLSS project database.
- Develop and populate a new directory section for educators, which includes identifying individuals and groups for inclusion, sending survey forms, updating individual records for the database, and developing new search features on the Directory website.
- Continue maintenance and expansion of the on-line Directory.

4.5 Internet Media Archive

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been compiled for various purposes and are now shared through the Internet via the IMA. The contents of the IMA are organized by the contributor's name, by event, or by organization. All of the media available in the archive are accompanied by information about the content, the contributor or source, and usage requirements.

The accomplishments since April 2005 and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance of the Internet Media Archive from April through August 2006.

Accomplishments

- The Internet Media Archive currently contains 2987 photos and other media resources available to the public in 68 albums and 22 categories. These resources have been viewed 3441 times. An additional 9,057 resources in the archive are not yet publicly available. Further documentation is being entered or gathered for these resources and when the information is complete they also will become publicly accessible.
- Archived the majority of the extensive ARCUS collection of audio and video resources from various workshops and scientific meetings and education and outreach activities from 2001 to the present.
- Posted all photos for which permission has been received to the online archive, with detailed photo information, photographer contact information, use criteria, and keywords for the search interface.

Planned Activities

- Announce the Internet Media Archive via ArcticInfo.
- Continue to gather and add to the collection of arctic-related images and other media resources and continue research and data entry of relevant information about source, subject, dates, research project, and funding source for all of the images.
- Maintain communication with the contributors and potential contributors to solicit contributions and timely and detailed information about the media resources.
- Continue video- and audio-recording of relevant meetings, workshops, and programmatic activities for inclusion in the Internet Media Archive.
- Obtain use permissions, attribution, and detailed information for the entire ARCUS image collection.
- Identify or produce additional figures, photographs, and maps depicting arctic research-related information. Develop short abstracts that explain each scientific figure and that provide information necessary for attribution, as well as citations for source material and other related references.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

ARCUS conducts a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic as a region.

The accomplishments since April 2005 and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. The supplemental funds requested would support outreach activities from April through August 2006, primarily the *Arctic Forum 2006* scheduled for May 2006, for which planning has already begun.

Accomplishments

- Planned and hosted the 1.5-day *Arctic Forum* conference in conjunction with ARCUS' 17th Annual Meeting in Washington, D.C. in May 2005. The topic of the *Forum* was "Arctic Climate Change and Public Literacy: What's at Stake?" The *Forum* was co-chaired by Dr. Stephanie Pfirman of Barnard College and Dr. Bruce Forbes of the University of Lapland. A two-minute video was developed by ARCUS staff in Spring 2005 with material from past *Arctic Forum* sessions to advertise *Arctic Forum 2005* and was distributed via the ARCUS website. *Arctic Forum 2005* was announced to the international arctic research community and registration and abstract submissions solicited via ArcticInfo and *Witness the Arctic*.
 - *Arctic Forum 2005* attracted 151 participants and included arctic researchers from the U.S. and other countries, policy makers, media representatives, federal agency personnel, and arctic residents, including significant representation from indigenous arctic communities.
 - The *Forum* was video-streamed via the Internet and followed by an international audience beyond those in attendance in Washington, D.C. Participants viewing the *Forum* via the video-stream were able to email questions and comments for the presenters to the co-chairs and ARCUS staff for inclusion in session discussions.
 - Plenary, panel, and poster presentations and discussions addressed topics such as: current science on arctic climate change and future scenarios; public and media perception of arctic climate change; communication strategies and their effectiveness; and the role of the research community in public literacy.
 - Presentations from the meeting are available on the ARCUS *Arctic Forum* website as downloadable Powerpoint or PDF files. Edited video and audio files from the *Arctic Forum 2005* presentations and sessions are available on the Internet Media Archive.
 - As a result of the success and vigor of the conference discussions, participants communicated to co-chairs and organizers a considerable interest in continuing a similar dialogue at the 2006 *Arctic Forum* and through additional community activities.
- Published the *Arctic Forum 2005* abstract volume; the volume is available online as a PDF and 750 copies were printed for distribution.
- Developed information resources such as flyers, brochures, and posters regarding arctic research activities and priorities; participated in outreach activities at scientific meetings and workshops to inform the broader scientific community and policy and decision-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings.
- Participated in or sponsored arctic outreach activities at the September 2005 AAAS Arctic Science Conference in Kodiak, Alaska, the Fall 2005 Meeting of AGU in San Francisco, California, and at other relevant meetings and workshops.

Planned Activities

- Convene a 1.5-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 18th Annual Meeting in Washington, DC in May 2006. The focus of the *Arctic Forum 2006* will be "International Arctic Research at a Turning Point: Innovations and Collaborations for the Future," a theme

that directly builds on the topic and success of *Arctic Forum 2005*. Dr. Craig Tweedie of the University of Texas at El Paso and Dr. Volker Rachold of the International Arctic Science Committee will chair the 2006 *Arctic Forum*.

- Plenary, panel, and poster presentations and discussions will focus on perspectives and solutions to enable arctic researchers to successfully forge and maintain novel innovations and international partnerships.
 - Specific topics to be addressed include: keys to success regarding challenging issues such as stakeholder involvement, multi- and interdisciplinary research, training the next generation of scientists, technological innovations, and data management.
- Publish and distribute the 2006 *Arctic Forum* abstract volume.
 - Prepare posters or presentations on request and participate in major scientific meetings or workshops to provide information and outreach regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support the overall tasks and the projects and activities included in each task of the cooperative agreement. This category was initiated to ensure stability and continuity of the direct activities that support the whole of the cooperative agreement so they are not vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year throughout the agreement.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization and the Executive Director is closely involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the cooperative agreement. She is directly involved in working with science steering committees and research community contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning, programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and project activities. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual program plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of NSF activities and projects, it is more difficult to allocate much of this time specifically to any

one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct management costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure (computer hardware and software required to maintain the network and server for the databases and listserves that support NSF-funded activities), high-speed Internet, and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the arctic research community under the cooperative agreement.

The major accomplishments since April 2005 and planned activities from now through August 2006 are listed below. Activities planned from January through March 2006 do not require supplemental funding. The supplemental funds requested would support Core activities from April through August 2006.

Accomplishments

- Coordinated planning, managed emerging priorities, and supervised work on all the tasks and project activities described in this report. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category rather than to individual projects.
- Upgraded hardware, software, and programming to expand capability for projects that require expanded server, network, and database capacity, support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information distribution.
- Managed the server setup, network, creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category. System upgrades included:
 - Performed Web server backend upgrades for PHP and MySQL plus applications relying on those packages.
 - Overhauled the email server spam prevention system, switching to the ASSP (Anti-Spam SMTP Proxy) software.
 - Overhauled and expanded the network backup system, including software upgrades and adding a backup server to greatly expand capacity.
 - Set up and tested software to for ARCUS Community Workspace Server, using the Plone content management system.
 - Created multiple new email lists on the List Server machine and performed minor software upgrades on the server.
 - Replaced the Flexmail web email form processor (concerns included security and performance issues) with custom-built PHP form processor.
 - Performed a number of other software and hardware upgrades to increase system and network efficiency and security.
 - Researched, purchased, and set up an Epson 9600 large format printer, used for printing posters and banners for NSF-funded projects. The on-site availability of the large format printer has considerably reduced the cost of producing posters for various projects.

-
- Supported staff travel to arctic research meetings and workshops that addressed topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which were not specific to one project.

Planned Activities

- Coordinate planning, prioritization and supervision of work on all the tasks and projects described in the projected activities, the program plan and budget for 2005-2006. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Continue to research and upgrade hardware, software and programming required to expand the interactive and dynamic capabilities of such projects as Arctic GIS, SEARCH, the ARCSS Program, the Arctic Social Sciences Program, TREC, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, ArcticInfo, the Calendar, the Internet Media Archive, interactive real-time online seminars and meetings, interactive bulletin boards, meeting registration and abstract submission, streamed audio and video content, and general information.
- Manage the server setup, network, and creation of needed technical resources and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to direct activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Support staff participation at arctic research meetings and workshops on topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which are not specific to one project.

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over fifteen years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents that reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this request for supplemental funds support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and provide information and support for the conduct of arctic research and, therefore, will contribute to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research supported by the National Science Foundation.

This supplement of \$1,188,044 to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279) is necessary because of several new activities that ARCUS will undertake on behalf of the arctic research community and the National Science Foundation (NSF). This supplement request also extends the expiration date of the award to 31 August 2006 to accommodate key events and transitional activities that must continue beyond the end of the current expiration date of this cooperative agreement, 31 March 2006.

The additional funding and extension are required because of needs that have emerged as projects have progressed. The request for a supplement is also necessary because several crucial activities would otherwise overlap the ending of the current five-year cooperative agreement and the beginning of a potential new funding award without adequate time to develop, submit, review, and process the ARCUS proposal for work to be performed through another five-year agreement.

All of the activities described in the supplement request summary and the budget justification are in keeping with, and part of, ARCUS' work for the NSF to provide organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs.

ARCUS is submitting this supplement request to undertake these new or additional activities at the request of and on behalf of NSF and the arctic research community, the SEARCH Interagency Program Management Committee, the ARCSS Committee, and other participants in and managers of aspects of arctic research. The specific activities and the support that will be provided have been discussed with the relevant NSF Program Managers as well.

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	5.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 40,950			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	5.00	0.00	0.00	40,950			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (10) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	5.00	0.00	0.00	192,736			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				1,711			
5. (3) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				36,258			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				271,655			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)				103,231			
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				374,886			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT				0			
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)				50,588			
2. FOREIGN				0			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____	800						
2. TRAVEL _____	85,500						
3. SUBSISTENCE _____	80,500						
4. OTHER _____	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (95) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS				166,800			
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				17,015			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				19,165			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				32,584			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				6,750			
5. SUBAWARDS				167,551			
6. OTHER				71,700			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				314,765			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				907,039			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 38.0000, Base: 739488)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				281,005			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				1,188,044			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$ 1,188,044			
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY		
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)	
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted
					NSF Funded Person-months	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				CAL	ACAD	SUMR
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director				5.00	0.00	0.00
2.						
3.						
4.						
5.						
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				5.00	0.00	0.00
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)						
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES				0.00	0.00	0.00
2. (10) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				5.00	0.00	0.00
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS						0
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS						1,711
5. (3) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)						36,258
6. (0) OTHER						0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)						271,655
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)						103,231
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)						374,886
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)						
TOTAL EQUIPMENT						0
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)						50,588
2. FOREIGN						0
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS						
1. STIPENDS \$ <u>800</u>						
2. TRAVEL <u>85,500</u>						
3. SUBSISTENCE <u>80,500</u>						
4. OTHER <u>0</u>						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (95) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS						166,800
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS						
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES						17,015
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION						19,165
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES						32,584
4. COMPUTER SERVICES						6,750
5. SUBAWARDS						167,551
6. OTHER						71,700
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS						314,765
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)						907,039
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)						
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)						281,005
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)						1,188,044
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)						0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)						\$ 1,188,044 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$		
PI/PI NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY		
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION		
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

Summary - Supplement Request ARC-0101279

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION

12/31/05 16:33 4/1/2005 to 08/31/05

1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING	
1.1 Arctic Logistics	
1.2 Alias Website	
1.3 GIS Planning	
1.4a SEARCH Planning	195422
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support	
1.5 Bering Sea Planning	20538
1.6 Workshop TBD	
1.7 SEARCH Brochure	
1.8 Arctic Data Coordination	0
Subtotal Direct Costs	215960
Indirect Costs	55255
	<u>271215</u>
2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION	
2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	0
2.2 <i>ARCSS Program Coordination</i>	
2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination	226370
2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop	
2.2.3 HARC SMO	
2.2.4 Arctic Hydrology Report	
Subtotal 2.2 Direct Costs	<u>226370</u>
2.3 <i>ASSP Program Coordination</i>	
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Planning	23709
2.3.2 Greenland Book	
2.3.3 Arctic Social Sciences Volume	
2.3.4 Bering Sea Community Planning	18060
Subtotal 2.3 Direct Costs	<u>41769</u>
Sub-total Direct Costs	268139
Indirect Costs	65033
	<u>333172</u>
3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION	
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	0
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers	12150
3.3 Arctic Science Education Report	
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE!	
3.5 TREC	44275
Subtotal Direct Costs	56425
Indirect Costs	21441
	<u>77866</u>
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH	
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters	25391
4.2 Website/ Internet Resources	54835
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserv	15935
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	7821
4.5 Internet Media Archive	18434
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach	100332
4.7 Publication: The Arctic	
4.8 Endangered Species Bulletin	
Subtotal Direct Costs	222748
Indirect Costs	84645
	<u>307393</u>
5 CORE SUPPORT	
Core Support	143767
Subtotal Direct Costs	0
Indirect Costs	54631
	198398
TOTAL	1188044
Estimated Indirect Cost Rate	38.00%

**Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Budget Explanation - Supplement Request ARC-0101279**

Total

1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.4a <u>SEARCH Planning</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	72,331	72,331
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	5,325	5,325
Participant Support Costs	35,500	35,500
Materials and Supplies	200	200
Publications/Dissemination	315	315
Consulting	-	-
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	70,551	70,551
Other Direct Costs	11,200	11,200
Total direct costs	<u>195,422</u>	<u>195,422</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>47,451</u>	<u>47,451</u>
	<u>242,873</u>	<u>242,873</u>
1.5 <u>Bering Sea Planning</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	6,460	6,460
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,775	1,775
Participant Support Costs	7,100	7,100
Materials and Supplies	40	40
Publications/Dissemination	63	63
Consulting	-	-
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	5,100	5,100
Total direct costs	<u>20,538</u>	<u>20,538</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>7,804</u>	<u>7,804</u>
	<u>28,342</u>	<u>28,342</u>
Subtotal Direct	215,960	215,960
Subtotal Indirect	55,255	55,255
Total Community Science Planning	<u>271,215</u>	<u>271,215</u>

2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1 <u>ARCSS Coordination</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	38,409	38,409
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	6,213	6,213
Participant Support Costs	57,625	57,625
Materials and Supplies	300	300
Publications/Dissemination	573	573
Consulting	10,000	10,000
Computer Services	6,250	6,250
Subcontracts	85,000	85,000
Other Direct Costs	22,000	22,000
Total direct costs	<u>226,370</u>	<u>226,370</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>53,721</u>	<u>53,721</u>
	<u>280,091</u>	<u>280,091</u>

ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.3.1 <u>Arctic Social Sciences Directory</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	6,709	6,709
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-
Consulting	5,000	5,000
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	12,000	12,000
Other Direct Costs	-	-
Total direct costs	<u>23,709</u>	<u>23,709</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>4,449</u>	<u>4,449</u>
	<u>28,158</u>	<u>28,158</u>

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	<u>Total</u>	
2.3.4 <u>Bering Sea Community Planning</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	6,410	6,410
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	3,550	3,550
Participant Support Costs	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	5,500	5,500
Consulting	-	-
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	2,600	2,600
Total direct costs	<u>18,060</u>	<u>18,060</u>
Total indirect costs	6,863	6,863
	<u>24,923</u>	<u>24,923</u>
Subtotal Direct Costs	268,139	268,139
Subtotal Indirect Costs	65,033	65,033
Total Arctic Sciences Section	<u>333,172</u>	<u>333,172</u>

3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.2 <u>Arctic Visiting Speakers</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	4,150	4,150
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-
Participant Support Costs	8,000	8,000
Materials and Supplies	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-
Consulting	-	-
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-
Total direct costs	<u>12,150</u>	<u>12,150</u>
Total indirect costs	4,617	4,617
	<u>16,767</u>	<u>16,767</u>

3.5 TREC

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	23,575	23,575
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-
Participant Support Costs	14,200	14,200
Materials and Supplies	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-
Consulting	6,500	6,500
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-
Total direct costs	<u>44,275</u>	<u>44,275</u>
Total indirect costs	16,824	16,824
	<u>61,099</u>	<u>61,099</u>

Subtotal Direct Costs	56,425	56,425
Subtotal Indirect Costs	21,441	21,441
Total Arctic Science Education	<u>77,866</u>	<u>77,866</u>

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	<u>Total</u>	
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH		
4.1 <u>Witness the Arctic Newsletters</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	25,291	25,291
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-
Materials and Supplies	100	100
Publications/Dissemination	-	-
Consulting	-	-
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-
Total direct costs	25,391	25,391
Total indirect costs	9,649	9,649
	35,040	35,040
4.2 <u>ARCUS Internet Resources</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	51,918	51,918
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-
Consulting	2,917	2,917
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-
Total direct costs	54,835	54,835
Total indirect costs	20,837	20,837
	75,672	75,672
4.3 <u>ArcticInfo Listserver</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	15,935	15,935
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-
Consulting	-	-
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-
Total direct costs	15,935	15,935
Total indirect costs	6,055	6,055
	21,990	21,990
4.4 <u>Directory of Arctic Researchers</u>		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	3,821	3,821
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-
Consulting	4,000	4,000
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-
Total direct costs	7,821	7,821
Total indirect costs	2,972	2,972
	10,793	10,793

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	<u>Total</u>	
4.5 Internet Media Archive		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,434	18,434
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-
Consulting	-	-
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-
Total direct costs	<u>18,434</u>	<u>18,434</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>7,005</u>	<u>7,005</u>
	<u>25,439</u>	<u>25,439</u>
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	5,063	5,063
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic)	17,750	17,750
Participant Support Costs	44,375	44,375
Materials and Supplies	250	250
Publications/Dissemination	7,894	7,894
Consulting	-	-
Computer Services	-	-
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	25,000	25,000
Total direct costs	<u>100,332</u>	<u>100,332</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>38,126</u>	<u>38,126</u>
	<u>138,458</u>	<u>138,458</u>
Subtotal Direct	222,748	222,748
Subtotal Indirect	84,645	84,645
Total Information and Outreach	<u>307,393</u>	<u>307,393</u>
5 CORE SUPPORT		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	96,380	96,380
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	15,975	15,975
Participant Support Costs	-	-
Materials and supplies	16,125	16,125
Publications/Dissemination	4,820	4,820
Consulting	4,167	4,167
Computer Services	500	500
Subcontracts	-	-
Other Direct Costs	5,800	5,800
Total direct costs	<u>143,767</u>	<u>143,767</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>54,631</u>	<u>54,631</u>
Total Core Support	<u>198,398</u>	<u>198,398</u>
Total Direct Costs all tasks	907,039	907,039
Total Indirect Costs all tasks	281,005	281,005
Total All Tasks	<u>1,188,044</u>	<u>1,188,044</u>
TOTAL		
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	374,886	374,886
Permanent Equipment	-	-
Travel	50,588	50,588
Participant Support Costs	166,800	166,800
Materials and Supplies	17,015	17,015
Publications/Dissemination	19,165	19,165
Consulting	32,584	32,584
Computer Services	6,750	6,750
Subcontracts	167,551	167,551
Other Direct Costs	71,700	71,700
Total direct costs	<u>907,039</u>	<u>907,039</u>
Indirect Costs @ 38.0%	<u>281,005</u>	<u>281,005</u>
Total direct and indirect	<u>1,188,044</u>	<u>1,188,044</u>

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279). The request for a supplement of \$1,188,044 to the funding already awarded includes a request to extend the expiration date of the award to 31 August 2006. The additional funding and extension are required because of emerging needs as projects have progressed and because several crucial activities would otherwise overlap the ending of the current five-year cooperative agreement and the beginning of a potential new funding award without adequate time to develop, submit, review, and process the ARCUS proposal for work to be performed through another five-year agreement.

All of the activities described in the supplement request summary and this budget justification are in keeping with, and part of, ARCUS' work for the National Science Foundation (NSF) to provide organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs.

ARCUS is submitting this supplement request to undertake these new or additional activities at the request of and on behalf of NSF and the arctic research community, the SEARCH Interagency Program Management Committee, the ARCSS Committee, and other participants in and managers of aspects of arctic research. The specific activities and the support that will be provided have been discussed with the relevant NSF Program Managers as well.

Item A: Senior Personnel

Funding totaling \$40,950 for current staff through 31 August 2006 is requested.

Item B: Other Personnel

Resources are requested for a total of 14 staff positions for five additional months. Personnel salaries and benefits required to continue to develop, coordinate and manage the activities described in the supplement request summary total \$230,705.

Item C: Fringe Benefits

ARCUS charges actual fringe benefits costs on direct salaries. The fringe rate for budgeting purpose is 38% and totals \$103,231.

Items E and F: Travel and Participant Support

Additional resources are requested for participant support for a SEARCH Science Steering Committee, a Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) planning meeting, and several associated meetings related to ARCSS Program planning, including a PI workshop for investigators funded under the Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) announcement of opportunity. In addition, funds are requested for participant support and staff travel support to convene the annual Arctic Forum. Participant and Travel Support totals 124 attendees at a cost of \$217,388.

Item G: Other Direct Costs

Line 1. Materials and Supplies

Resources are requested to support the typical materials costs for a five-month supplemental period.

Line 2. Publication/Documentation and Dissemination

The cost of printing several publications for distribution to the community, including *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Plan* will be \$8,500. Additional postage and distribution costs for products of all projects included in this supplement request total \$10,665.

Line 3. Consultant Services

Consultant Services, including programming, research, editing and writing, and facilitation costs will contribute to TREC, Arctic Social Science Directory, Directory of Arctic Researchers, Website Development, and Core Support, totaling \$32,584.

Line 4. Computer Services

Computer support services for all of the activities included in the supplement request total \$6,250. An additional \$500 will be spent in the area of Core Support.

Line 5. Subcontracts

Continuation of subcontracts to support the ARCSS Program, including the HARC project office and support for the ARCSS Committee chair, and a new subcontract for SNACS coordination, plus support through SEARCH for the chair of the ASOF program will cost \$167,551.

Line 6. Other

Resources totaling \$71,700 are requested to cover the cost of conference, workshop, and meeting support and other miscellaneous expenses for the participants at SEARCH and ARCSS meetings, the BEST meeting and the Bering Sea Community forum, and the Arctic Forum.

Item I: Indirect Costs (rate/base)

The ARCUS maximum provisional rate is currently 38%. The ARCUS NSF cooperative agreement allows charging of indirect costs to Participant Support, which has been kept in the base of \$739,488.